

GAS search

Medline

Search terms

- 1 (goal? adj (set or setting or attainment or scale\$ or scaling)).ti,ab,kw.
- 2 Self Care/
- 3 self-care.ti,ab.
- 4 self-set.ti,ab.
- 5 self-assigned.ti,ab.
- 6 (individual adj3 goal\$).ti,ab.
- 7 goals/
- 8 goal\$.ti,ab.
- 9 7 or 8
- 10 2 or 3 or 4 or 5
- 11 9 and 10
- 12 1 or 6 or 11
- 13 randomized controlled trial.pt.
- 14 controlled clinical trial.pt.
- 15 randomized.ab.
- 16 placebo.ab.
- 17 drug therapy.fs.
- 18 drug therapy.fs.
- 19 trial.ab.
- 20 groups.ab.
- 21 Epidemiologic studies/
- 22 exp case control studies/
- 23 exp cohort studies/
- 24 Case control.tw.
- 25 (cohort adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 26 (cohort adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 27 (cohort adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 28 (observational adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 29 Longitudinal.tw.
- 30 Retrospective.tw.
- 31 Cross sectional.tw.
- 32 Cross-sectional studies/
- 33 or/13-32
- 34 12 and 33
- 35 (individual* adj5 goal\$).ti,ab.
- 36 33 and 35
- 37 34 or 36

Embase

Search terms

- 1 (goal? adj (set or setting or attainment or scale\$ or scaling)).ti,ab,kw.
- 2 exp *self care/
- 3 self-care.ti,ab.
- 4 self-set.ti,ab.
- 5 self-assigned.ti,ab.
- 6 (individual\$ adj5 goal\$).ti,ab.
- 7 exp *motivation/
- 8 goal\$.ti,ab.
- 9 7 or 8
- 10 2 or 3 or 4 or 5
- 11 9 and 10
- 12 1 or 6 or 11
crossover procedure/ or double-blind procedure/ or single-blind procedure/ or randomized
controlled trial/ or crossover\$.ti,ab,ot. or cross over\$.ti,ab,ot. or placebo\$.ti,ab,ot. or (doubl\$
adj blind\$).ti,ab,ot. or allocat\$.ti,ab,ot. or random\$.ti,ab,ab. or trial\$.ti.
- 13
- 14 *Clinical study/
- 15 *Case control study/
- 16 *Family study/
- 17 *Longitudinal study/
- 18 *Retrospective study/
- 19 *Prospective study/
- 20 *Cohort analysis/
- 21 (Cohort adj (study or studies)).mp.
- 22 (Case control adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 23 (follow up adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 24 (observational adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 25 (epidemiologic\$ adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 26 (cross sectional adj (study or studies)).tw.
- 27 or/13-26
- 28 12 and 27
- 29 limit 28 to (conference abstract or conference proceeding)
- 30 28 not 29

PsycINFO

Search terms

- 1 (goal? adj (set or setting or attainment or scale\$ or scaling)).ti,ab,tm.
- 2 exp Self Management/
- 3 self-care.ti,ab.
- 4 self-set.ti,ab.
- 5 self-assigned.ti,ab.
- 6 (individual\$ adj5 goal\$).ti,ab.
- 7 exp Goals/
- 8 goal\$.ti,ab.

- 9 7 or 8
- 10 2 or 3 or 4 or 5
- 11 9 and 10
- 12 1 or 6 or 11
((case* adj5 control*) or (case adj3 comparison*) or case-comparison or control
- 13 group*).ti,ab,id. not "Literature Review".md.
((cohort or longitudinal or prospective or retrospective).ti,ab,id. or longitudinal study.md. or
- 14 prospective study.md. or retrospective study.md.) not "Literature Review".md.
- 15 (cross section* or "prevalence study").ti,ab,id.
clinical trials/ or "treatment outcome clinical trial".md. or ((randomi?ed adj7 trial*) or
- 16 ((single or doubl* or tripl* or treb*) and (blind* or mask*)) or (controlled adj3 trial*) or
- 17 (clinical adj2 trial*).ti,ab,id.
- 18 13 or 14 or 15 or 16
- 19 12 and 17
- 19 limit 18 to peer reviewed journal